

Uncovering the Ethical Role of True Veterinarian

Aarti Nirwan¹, Jayesh Vyas¹, Urmila Pannu²

¹Teaching Associate in Department of Animal Genetics and Breeding, College of Veterinary and Animal Science, Bikaner

²Professor and Head of Department of Animal Genetics and Breeding, College of Veterinary and Animal Science, Bikaner

Corresponding author: aartinirwan14@gmail.com

Abstract

The profession of veterinarians can be described as an outline of an ethically challenging job; they have to deal with decisions that incorporate moral aspects. This recognition is specifically true for veterinarian's professional field. The practice of veterinary medicine is fixed in a compound ethical structure that is identified at least by demands of professional obligations, animal patients, animal owners and society as a whole. Equally the moral challenges and conflicts may be most common source of stress and poor well-being. However, there is still intermediate understanding of what veterinarians consider as morally challenging situations in their daily routine work. The aim of this review article for better understanding of moral value and ethical role of true veterinarians to shed light on this context.

Highlights

- Key moral challenges for veterinarians are situations in which their profession conflict with obstacles.
- Essential challenges can be described as a role of true veterinarian rather than their economic concern.
- Vital moral challenges can be expressed as the conflict between different roles of veterinarians.

What is a Veterinarian exactly?

A veterinarian, who protects the health and well-being of animals as a profession. They treat sick and injured animals as well as diagnose and control

animal diseases. They also advise owners on proper care of their pets and livestock. A wide range of services provided by veterinarian in government service, public health, private practice, private industry, teaching, research, military service, and other related areas.

What qualities do you need to be a veterinarian?

Every professional depend on specific skills and veterinarians are same as these. They should possess compassion, purposeful, manual dexterity, and soft communication skills. Being a animal doctor they should be able to effectively communicate goes beyond when they interacting with animals. So, that only Potential candidates interested in following the veterinary field as a career or have to realize that if they don't get along with other people, they should not be in the field of veterinary.

What is the career outlook for veterinarians?

A career in veterinary having a passion for animals is a fantastic reason to pursue in this field. On top of that, it's a growing field with plenty of opportunity. Veterinarians are poised to

see substantial growth in the coming years, as a increased pet expenditures and a need for professionals who can maintain a safe food supply. According to the US Bureau of Labor Statistics, veterinarian employment is expected to grow by 17% through 2030. This far outpaces the average for all professions.

What does Veterinarian duties?

When taking the veterinarian's oath, a veterinarian solemnly swears to use his or her scientific knowledge and skills "for the benefit of society, through the protection of animal health, the relief of animal suffering, the conservation of animal resources, the promotion of public health, and the advancement of medical knowledge."

A veterinarian's duties could include:

- Examine animal health issues
- Vaccinating against several diseases, such as immune response and rabies
- Diagnosis and medication of animals suffering from illnesses or infections
- Treating and dressing wounds
- Treating and dressing wounds
- Cure fractures
- Depending on training, Performing minor to complex surgery
- Proper counseling of owners about animal feeding, breeding and behavior
- Euthanizing animals when its needed
- Providing preventive care to maintain the health of livestock
- Performing diagnostic tests such as X-ray, EKG, ultrasound, blood and urine.

Am I actually a veterinarian or an economist?

The veterinary profession increased concern as a duty for animal welfare seems one of the answers to deal with the complex of societal expectations regarding veterinary responsibilities. However, if this would turn into a one-dimensional focus on either animal welfare or economics, it would do no justice to the broader spectrum of public expectations towards the veterinarian. This is not only a public expectation; it is also acknowledged as a professional responsibility by the profession. Veterinarians are expected to promote public health and the health of the environment too. It is broadly recognized that with their cross-species pathobiological expertise, veterinarians can make a valuable benefaction to public health.

Is veterinary field needed to collaborate with one health frame work?

Veterinarians play an essential role in the animal-based food chain. In the last decades, food scandals and zoonotic disease outbreaks have shown how much animal and human health is entangled. So that they are professionally responsible for the health of farm animals to secure food safety and public health. Therefore, the concept of One Health is broadly promoted within veterinary medicine. The profession embraces this idea that the health of humans, animals and the environment is inextricably linked and supports the related call for transdisciplinary collaboration. Especially in zoonotic disease control, the benefits of the cooperation between veterinarians and human doctors seem evident.

However, applying a One Health approach also makes moral problems explicit. For instance, how should veterinarians deal with situations in which measures to protect public health negatively affect animal health? This creates a conflict of professional responsibilities. To deal with such moral problems and to strengthen the veterinarian's position, the starting point is a holistic perspective on One Health.

References

<https://www.sgu.edu/blog/veterinary/what-is-a-veterinarian/>

<https://www.careerexplorer.com/careers/veterinarian/>

Ministry of Agriculture, Nature and Food Quality. 2011. "Animal Law." Dutch government. 2011. https://wetten.overheid.nl/BWBR0030250/2019-01_01#Hoofdstuk4_Artike14.2. Accessed 28 Jan 2019.

British Veterinary Association (BVA). 2016. Animal welfare policy position. London. <https://www.bva.co.uk/News-campaigns-and-policy/Policy/Ethics-and-welfare/Animal-welfare/>. Accessed 28 Jan 2019.

Davies, P. 2017. Balancing responsibilities when prescribing antimicrobials for farm animals. *Veterinary Record* 180 (15): 374–375. <https://doi.org/10.1136/vr.j1708>.

Dürnberger, C. (2020). Am I actually a veterinarian or an economist? Understanding the moral challenges for farm veterinarians in Germany on the basis of a qualitative online survey. *Research in Veterinary Science*, 133, 246-250.

van Herten, J., & Meijboom, F. L. B. (2019). Veterinary responsibilities within the one health

framework. *Food ethics*, 3(1), 109-123.

Hernandez, E., Fawcett, A., Brouwer, E., Rau, J., & Turner, P. V. (2018). Speaking up: Veterinary ethical responsibilities and animal welfare issues in everyday practice. *Animals*, 8(1), 15.